

Catalytic action of water-miscible organic solvents on the hydrolytic degradation of phosphate glasses[†]

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A number of samples of sodium-nickel and sodium-copper copolyphosphate glasses having Na : Ni/Cu ratio 9 : 1 and 8 : 2 were prepared alongwith control samples of sodium polyphosphate. Their hydrolytic degradation catalyzed by six water – miscible organic solvents methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, *t*-butanol, acetone and dioxane at four different concentrations (10, 20, 30 and 40%, v/v) at 35° was studied. While the degradation in the case of control sodium polyphosphate increased with increasing concentrations of the organic solvents, the copolyphosphate glasses did not appear to undergo organic solvents, the copolyphosphate glasses did not appear to undergo organic solvent catalyzed hydrolytic degradation. Introduction of Cu²⁺ or Ni²⁺ ion in sodium polyphosphate chain apparently lowered their molecular weights and increased the cross-linked density of the glassy network to such an extent that no further degradation was possible in the presence of organic solvents. In sodium polyphosphate the percentage molecular weight loss was found to be larger in solvent media of lower dielectric constant.

Phosphate glasses have gained tremendous importance in industry¹⁻⁴ due to their low transformation temperatures and high thermal coefficients, as compared to silicate glasses⁵. Inorganic polyphosphate glasses are polymeric in nature⁶. The P–O–P bond in long-chain polyphosphates is as much of importance to an inorganic chemist as to a biochemist studying phosphorylation^{7,8}. This bond can be broken in a number of ways including hydrolysis⁹. Bhargava *et al.*¹⁰ studied the degradation of long-chain polyphosphate catalyzed by organic solvents. A detailed kinetic study of degradation on sodium polyphosphate glass in presence of six different solvents was carried out by Das *et al.*¹¹. Since the phenomenon involves heterogeneous catalysis with likelihood of the catalyst taking part in the reaction, it was interesting to observe the effect of concentration of the catalyst on the course of degradation. The present paper, therefore, deals with the studies on concentration-dependence of the organic solvents on the degradation of sodium poly- and copolyphosphate glasses.

Results and discussion

Sodium polyphosphate (NaPP), sodium copper copolyphosphate (NaCuPP) and sodium nickel copolyphosphate (NaNiPP) were used.

Weight average molecular weights obtained initially and after 2 h in different solvent media for NaPP samples are reported in Table 1. Table 2 gives an idea of the percentage

molecular weight-loss (W) in each case. This is defined by eqn. (1)¹²,

$$W = \frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_0 is the initial molecular weight of the samples and W_t after time t .

It can be seen that the value of W increases with increasing concentration of the organic solvent in each solvent medium. To fully appreciate the implications of the results obtained in this way let us look at the P–O–P linkages in polyphosphate chains which are thermodynamically unstable towards hydrolysis¹³. The equilibrium for the reaction,

lies well over to the right. It may be suggested that hydrolysis at branching points probably consists of nucleophilic attack by water molecules.

This, being the transition state, breaks down the polyphos-

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Table 1. Hydrolytic degradation data for NaPP samples after 2 h in water-miscible organic solvents at 35°

Sl. no.	Initial value of $\bar{M}_w (W_0)$	Concn. % (v/v)	Values of \bar{M}_w in different organic solvents (W_t)					
			Methanol	Ethanol	<i>n</i> -Propanol	<i>t</i> -Butanol	Acetone	Dioxane
1.	9200	10	8980	8980	8930	8880	8930	8810
		20	8930	8910	8880	8810	8750	8750
		30	8870	8850	8810	8750	8690	8680
		40	8800	8760	8720	8660	8580	8530
2.	9430	10	9250	9240	8190	9080	9140	9070
		20	9150	9095	9110	9020	9010	9050
		30	9100	9030	9010	8940	8920	8910
		40	9025	8930	8930	8840	8820	8800
3.	9770	10	9540	9570	9520	9430	9510	9370
		20	9450	9440	9430	9370	9330	9360
		30	9370	9360	9340	9290	9240	9220
		40	9340	9280	9250	9195	9140	9120
4.	9880	10	9680	9640	8590	9520	9640	9450
		20	9580	9560	9580	9430	9455	9480
		30	9490	9470	9490	9370	9335	9340
		40	9390	9380	9370	9260	9220	9210

phate chain by breaking one of the three equivalent P–O bonds.

In order to appreciate the role of water-miscible organic solvents in causing the hydrolytic degradation, we must look at the structure of the polyphosphate chain of the NaPP glass with $n(\text{PO}_3^-)$ ions or a polyanion $(\text{PO}_3^-)_n$,

The nucleophilic attack by OH^- ions on such a highly charge polyanion seems to be unfavorable, because the electrostatic repulsion between similar charges greatly decreases the entropy of activation¹⁴. However, if the dielectric constant of the medium decreases, it is expected that the rate of attack of a neutral molecule, like water, ethanol or some other nucleophilic organic molecule would increase. The rate of reactions will be larger in a medium of lower dielectric constant. Lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium leads to a loss of charge density which makes the nucleophilic attack easier. The mechanism of the solvent catalyzed degradation of long-chain polyphosphates for alcohols in general is given in Scheme 1 where (P) represents the rest of the chain in addition to the unit shown.

Reaction rates resulting from change of solvents are also known to depend on dipole moments of the solvent in question. In fact Dack¹⁵ has defined a parameter, the electro-

Scheme 1

static factor (EF) which is the product of dielectric constant ϵ and dipole moment μ . Based on its value, the solvents can be divided into four classes : (i) hydrocarbon (EF = 0–2), (ii) electron donor solvent (EF = 2–20), (iii) hydroxylic solvents (EF = 15–50) and (iv) dipolar aprotic solvents (EF >50). In the present investigation, four of the solvents in whose presence the hydrolytic degradation was studied belong to the class of hydroxylic solvents. They are methanol,

ethanol, *n*-propanol and *t*-butanol. Acetone belongs to the class of dipolar aprotic solvents while dioxane is neither a hydroxylic solvent nor a dipolar aprotic solvent. It is actually a solvent with zero dipole moment. The results of percentage molecular weight-loss for NaPP in all the six solvents are given in Table 2.

It is interesting to note (Table 2) that the hydrolytic degradation increases in the case of hydroxylic solvents as we go from methanol to *t*-butanol. The rate of degradation also increases in the case of acetone and dioxane. In dioxane the degradation is maximum. Hydrolytic degradation is also seen to increase with increase in the concentration of the solvent catalyzing it. Clearly, the catalyst organic solvent in each case takes part in the reaction. The mechanisms proposed for the degradation reaction by different organic solvents involve the formation of an unstable complex ion by the combination of organic solvents and a part of the

polyphosphate chain as an intermediate. The results given in Table 2 amply corroborate the mechanism in with the solvent acting as a catalyst takes part in the reaction.

Thus NaPP samples prepared simultaneously as control alongwith copolyphosphate glasses are seen to undergo hydrolytic degradation due to catalytic action of different water-miscible organic solvents while copolyphosphates remain unaffected. One reason for this could be the fact that the introduction of Ni²⁺ or Cu²⁺ as counter cations into the main chain of sodium polyphosphate causes lowering of molecular weight to such an extent that no further degradation is possible (Table 3). Any cation other than sodium in the main chain whether as counter cation or dopant somehow act as chain terminator¹⁶. Additionally, cations Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ probably also cause significant increase in chain stiffness which provide stability to the low molecular weight fragments of the copolyphosphate glasses. This explana-

Table 2. Percentage molecular weight-loss in different NaPP samples after 2 h of hydrolytic degradation at 35°

Organic solvents in water (% v/v)		Percentage mol. wt. loss (<i>W</i>)*			
		$\bar{M}_w = 9200$	$\bar{M}_w = 9430$	$\bar{M}_w = 9770$	$\bar{M}_w = 9880$
Methanol	10	2.39	2.90	2.85	2.97
	20	2.93	2.96	3.27	3.03
	30	3.59	3.49	4.09	3.95
	40	4.35	4.29	4.40	4.85
Ethanol	10	2.89	3.01	3.04	3.42
	20	3.19	3.25	3.23	3.84
	30	3.80	4.25	4.19	4.15
	40	4.78	5.30	5.01	5.06
<i>n</i> -Propanol	10	2.98	3.59	3.61	3.53
	20	3.47	3.89	3.88	3.83
	30	4.24	4.35	4.40	4.25
	40	4.78	5.30	5.02	5.06
<i>t</i> -Butanol	10	3.54	3.65	3.42	3.64
	20	4.18	4.29	4.10	4.55
	30	4.89	5.19	4.91	5.16
	40	5.87	6.29	5.89	6.28
Acetone	10	3.93	3.91	3.66	3.42
	20	4.389	4.40	4.50	4.30
	30	5.54	5.41	5.43	5.52
	40	6.74	6.42	6.54	6.63
Dioxane	10	4.23	3.81	4.09	4.04
	20	4.89	4.02	4.19	4.35
	30	5.65	5.51	5.63	5.47
	40	7.23	6.68	6.65	6.73

$$*W = \frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0} \times 100$$

Table 3. Molecular weights NaNiPP and NaCuPP

Sample no.	Mol. ratio*	Temp. of prepn. $\pm 10^\circ$	Duration of heating (h)	Mol. Wt., M_c	
				NaNiPP	NaCuPP
1.	9 : 1	700	2	1110	1540
	8 : 2			930	1080
2.	9 : 1	700	3	1320	1620
	8 : 2			1130	1160
3.	9 : 1	700	4	1430	1710
	8 : 2			1240	1320
4.	9 : 1	800	2	1180	1560
	8 : 2			950	1110
5.	9 : 1	800	3	1400	1670
	8 : 2			1140	1220
6.	9 : 1	800	4	1540	1840
	8 : 2			1260	1390

*Na : Ni/Cu

tion finds further support when we look at the glass transition temperature values of copolyphosphate glasses as compared to control sodium polyphosphate samples prepared simultaneously. The T_g values of NaNiPP and NaCuPP are higher than those of NaPP¹⁷ which could be attributed to increase in crosslink density¹⁸. A possible structure of sodium polyphosphate glass may be shown in Fig. 1a. Incorporation of Cu^{2+} or Ni^{2+} into this sodium polyphosphate glass network appears to increase the crosslinking by getting attached to two non-bridging oxygen atoms of two different sodium polyphosphate chains as shown in Figs. 1b and 1c. This eventually increases the number of crosslinks in the glassy network structure of copolyphosphates and therefore their T_g values are found to be high.

Conclusions :

Hydrolytic degradation of long-chain polyphosphate is catalyzed by a number of water-miscible organic solvents. The present study carried out at 35° using methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, *t*-butanol, acetone and dioxane having 10, 20, 30 and 40% (v/v) concentrations reveals that the extent of degradation increases with increasing concentration of the organic solvent in water. The phenomenon, therefore, is an example of homogeneous catalysis. Sodium-nickel and sodium-copper copolyphosphates which have much lower molecular weights as compared to the control sodium polyphosphate samples do not undergo hydrolytic degrada-

Fig. 1. Schematic structures of sodium polyphosphate (1a) and sodium copolyphosphate glasses (1b and 1c) where $M^{2+} = \text{Cu}^{2+}$ or Ni^{2+} .

tion under similar conditions. Solvent with lower dielectric constant are more effective than others in catalyzing the degradation of NaPP.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the preparation of polyphosphate glasses were of A.R. grade. All the organic solvents employed were further purified by using standard methods¹⁹.

Poly- and copolyphosphate glasses : Preparation of sodium poly- and copolyphosphate glasses has been described in earlier communications¹⁷. While sodium polyphosphate glass was prepared by quenching the melt obtained by heating NaH_2PO_4 in a platinum dish in a muffle furnace, in the case of copolyphosphates, a mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$, carbonate of Ni/Cu and NaH_2PO_4 replaced pure NaH_2PO_4 . The temperature of preparation ($700\text{--}800^\circ$) was kept constant and the melts were quenched over ice-cooled stainless steel plates. The glassy nature of the samples were confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis.

Determination of molecular weights : For determining end-group molecular weight (M_c), equivalent to number average molecular weight, a 1% solution (30 ml) of the phosphate glass in conductivity water was titrated against a carbonate-free 0.1 N NaOH solution from pH 4–11.

A Systronics 333 pH meter was employed. Freshly prepared solutions were employed in the case of copolyphosphate samples, and sodium polyphosphate solutions were stored for 24 h before titration to allow disappearance of chain-branching²⁰. Copolyphosphate glasses do not have chain branching and low pH of sodium-copper copolyphosphate could lead to hydrolytic degradation on storage.

From the titration curve obtained by plotting pH against the volume of NaOH, the values of M_e were calculated by noting the volume of NaOH (A in ml), needed to titrate between two inflexion points,

$$M_e = \frac{20000 B}{A}$$

where B is the amount of the glass (in g) in the solution. The weight average molecular weights of sodium polyphosphate glasses were obtained viscometrically using an Ostwald viscometer (with a flow time of 130 s) at 35° and the relationship given by Strauss *et al.*²¹ for solutions in 0.035 N NaBr,

$$[\eta] = 1.76 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_w$$

Degradation studies :

Six different organic solvents, viz. methanol, ethanol, acetone, *t*-butanol, *n*-propanol and dioxane were chosen to study the hydrolytic degradation of NaPP, NaCuPP and NaNiPP glasses catalyzed by these water-miscible solvents. In all the cases 10, 20, 30 and 40% (v/v) organic solvents dissolved in double-distilled water were used as solvent media. The concentration of phosphate glasses in all the cases was kept at 1%.

In the case of NaNiPP and NaCuPP glasses, the flow time in the viscometer used for monitoring their hydrolytic degradation catalyzed by different organic solvents showed no change in the flow time even after 24 h. It could, therefore, be concluded that the NaNiPP and NaCuPP glasses do not undergo hydrolytic degradation in the presence of these water-miscible organic solvents.

The course of hydrolytic degradation in each solvent medium was observed by using four samples of NaPP having different molecular weights. In each case a 1% solution of the sample under investigation was taken in an Ostwald viscometer placed in a thermostatic water-bath maintained at 35° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$), Flow times were observed initially and after 2 h. Values of \bar{M}_w corresponding to the observed values of η_{sp}/c were calculated in each case.

For monitoring changes in molecular weights, plots of η_{sp}/c against \bar{M}_w were first drawn for each solvent medium by using four samples of NaPP. With fair approximation

these were straight-lines and the values of \bar{M}_w corresponding to that of η_{sp}/c at any stage could be obtained simply by interpolation of these plots.

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